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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**14-Electoral Behavioral Models in Sweden
and Norway: A Psychopolitical Perspective.
By Viktor Melnyk and others. p. 299.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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ELECTORAL BEHAVIORAL MODELS IN SWEDEN AND NORWAY: A PSYCHOPOLITICAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyses electoral behaviour in Norway and Sweden through the framework of three distinct models: an emotion-driven model (group-based voting), an individualistic model (economic voting), and an institutionally oriented model (trade union- or organisation-based voting). The findings contribute to the systematisation of voting trends among the Swedish and Norwegian electorates and provide insights into the geographical, economic, and psychopolitical factors influencing voting patterns. A mixed-methods research design was applied. Quantitative methods were applied to analyse electoral data, and qualitative methods were used to explore the psycho-behavioural factors underlying these voting patterns. The results of exit polls from the 2022 Swedish election highlight key issues shaping political engagement, distinguishing them based on ideological orientation and the policy agendas of specific electoral blocs. These issues include climate change threats, social exclusion, immigration, integration, and security. Ideological orientation, party allegiance, and political preferences are primary determinants of

voter behaviour, with motivation structured according to the Law of Effect. The article explores the interrelations between political parties and their electorates, analysing the effectiveness of various electoral campaign strategies. Changes in voter mobilisation approaches and the increasing politicisation of immigration have contributed to the emergence of a distinct subgroup within the group-based voting model. This phenomenon is particularly evident among ethnic and national minorities (e.g., individuals of migrant origin) and groups with varying educational backgrounds, as illustrated by the 2021 Norwegian parliamentary election context.

Keywords: elections, electoral behaviour, electoral behavioural model, Sweden, Norway, identity, political psychology.

1- INTRODUCTION

In political science and political psychology, electoral behaviour is considered a key indicator of the advancement and consolidation of democratic practices¹. It represents a structured and systematic form of civic participation in political processes, thus serving as a fundamental component of elections as a social institution². Paradoxically, the absence of bureaucratic coercion by the state often correlates with increased electoral engagement. Citizens are more inclined to vote in systems where the electoral process is characterised by minimal legal interference and regulation. In contrast, absenteeism tends to rise in states where compulsory voting is institutionalised or where bureaucratic oversight over electoral procedures is imposed, highlighting this counterintuitive dynamic³.

This paradox is exemplified by the political systems of modern Scandinavian monarchies compared to certain nations in Southern Europe⁴. In the Italian Republic, a mandatory voting system operated *de jure* between 1945 and 1993, but it failed to alleviate chronic political instability or frequent governmental turnover. Meanwhile, in the Hellenic Republic (Greece), mandatory voting remains a constitutional requirement, although it is not enforced. For example, voter turnout during the Greek parliamentary

¹ A. C. Salgado Lévano, “Conceptualización sobre psicología política y una mirada a sus investigaciones durante los últimos años”, *Liberabit (Lima)*, Vol. 12, No. 12 (2006), pp. 73–84. <http://www.scielo.org.pe/pdf/liber/v12n12/a08v12n12.pdf>

² O. Skrypniuk, O. Buriachenko, V. Melnyk, V. Kobko-Odaryi, O. Berezovska-Chmil, “Formation of Authoritarian and Democratic Political Regimes: Political and Legal Aspect”, *Lex Humana*, Vol. 15, No. 4 (2023), pp. 514–530. <https://seer.ucp.br/seer/index.php/LexHumana/article/view/2829>

³ G. Katz and I. Levin, “A General Model of Abstention Under Compulsory Voting”, *Political Science Research and Methods*, Vol. 6, No. 3 (2016), pp. 489–508. <https://doi.org/10.1017/psrm.2016.49>

⁴ L. Carrieri and M. Morini, “The Changing Structure of Political Conflicts in the South of Europe: An Analysis of Issue Voting in Four Countries”, *Political Studies Review*, Vol. 22, No. 1 (2022), pp. 55–76. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14789299221138030>

elections⁵. on May 21, 2023, was 60.94%. Despite this, the leading political forces called for a second election on June 25, 2023, during which voter turnout declined to 53.74%, reflecting a broader disengagement.

Despite these manifestations of political instability, neither Greece nor other Southern European nations have been hindered in their continued membership in the European Union, underscoring the difficulties of the relationship between electoral participation and the structural stability of political systems⁶.

The Kingdom of Sweden and the Kingdom of Norway rank among the select few nations globally where voter turnout consistently reaches or exceeds 75–80% of eligible voters, despite the absence of mandatory voting laws. During the 2022 *Riksdag* Election in the Kingdom of Sweden, voter turnout was recorded at an impressive 84.2%⁷. Similarly, the 2021 *Storting* Election in the Kingdom of Norway achieved a turnout of 77.2%⁸.

In the 2023 edition of The Economist Democracy Index, the Kingdom of Norway received an outstanding score of 9.8 out of 10, earning its position as the most democratic country in the world according to this metric. The Kingdom of Sweden closely followed with a score of 9.4⁹, ranking as the fourth most democratic country globally. The Economist Intelligence Unit classifies both nations as full democracies, a testament to their robust democratic systems and active civic participation.

In such contexts, where electoral absenteeism is rare and often viewed as socially irresponsible, it is crucial to understand the factors that drive voter participation¹⁰. This is particularly relevant because neither Sweden nor Norway imposes legal voting requirements. Instead, ideological differences – or at least perceived differences – among political parties serve as primary motivators for voter engagement. Analysing the policies and political stances that resonate with the electorate is essential to identifying the key determinants of voter turnout¹¹.

⁵ S. Verney and B. N. Field, “The 2023 Elections in Greece and Spain: Evolving Party Systems in Post-Crisis Southern Europe”, *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, Vol. 62 (2024), pp. 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.13658>

⁶ P. Artelaris, “The economic geography of European Union’s discontent: Lessons from Greece”, *European Urban and Regional Studies*, Vol. 29, No. 4 (2022), pp. 479–497. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09697764221101742>

⁷ Valpresentation, (n.d.). <https://resultat.val.se/val2022/RD?r=S>

⁸ Valgresultat, *Storting election data*, (2021). <https://valgresultat.no/valg/2021/st>

⁹ O. Skrypniuk, O. Buriachenko, V. Melnyk, V. Kobko-Odariy, O. Berezovska-Chmil, (2023).

¹⁰ L. Berg and H. Oscarsson, “The Swedish regional elections 2018”, *Regional & Federal Studies*, Vol. 30, No. 3 (2020), pp. 511–524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597566.2020.1739656>

¹¹ P. Söderlund, “Retrospective Voting and Electoral Volatility: A Nordic perspective”, *Scandinavian Political Studies*, Vol. 31, No. 2 (2008), pp. 217–240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9477.2008.00203.x>

Given the similarities in the party systems of Sweden and Norway¹². A joint, comprehensive analysis of electoral behaviour offers valuable insights as well as the commonalities among individual political parties in these nations. Swedish exit poll data provides a foundation for examining policy-driven voting dynamics, while Norwegian exit poll data highlights trends based on group identity¹³. Additionally, election outcomes in both countries offer opportunities to explore the geographical and economic factors influencing voting patterns.

By synthesising these datasets, researchers can address the question of voter motivation and identify the determinants of electoral activity through a comparative case study of Sweden and Norway. This integrated approach not only illuminates the complexity of voting behaviour in these democracies but also enhances our broader understanding of civic engagement in high-functioning democratic systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative techniques. Quantitative methods were applied to electoral data, particularly for analysing voting trends among Swedish and Norwegian electorates. Qualitative methods were used to explore the psycho-behavioural factors underlying these voting patterns.

Data analysis consisted of two primary types:

- Examining *election results* in the studied countries to identify voting patterns, focusing on electoral geography and regional economic data.
- An analysis of *exit polls* conducted on election days during the most recent parliamentary elections aimed at uncovering voting patterns based on voter demographics and the voting behaviour of different identity groups.

Behavioural methods were also employed to substantiate the psychological foundation of the study. Specifically, political ideologies and party affiliations were examined through *subject-object interaction*, as conceptualised in *organisational behaviour*. Ideological orientation, party allegiance, and political preferences were considered organising factors of behaviour, with voter motivation structured according to the *Law of Effect*. This means that promoting support for “one’s own” group, as opposed to others, is inherently programmed and tends toward collective reinforcement¹⁴.

¹² D. Arter, “The emergence of the Scandinavian party system(s)”, In *Manchester University Press eBooks*, (2013). <https://doi.org/10.7765/9781847792020.00010>

¹³ P. Bevelander and R. Pendakur, “Voting and social inclusion in Sweden. *International Migration*, Vol. 49, No. 4 (2010), pp. 67–92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2435.2010.00605.x>

¹⁴ J. Benson, “Democracy and the Epistemic Problems of Political Polarization”, *American Political Science Review*, Vol. 118, No. 4 (2024), pp. 1719–1732. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055423001089>

The organisational behaviour approach facilitated the differentiation of group-based, economic, and institutional voting as characteristic manifestations of political-psychological mobilisation in Sweden and Norway¹⁵.

To explore identities, we applied a *political anthropology framework*, emphasising the role of tradition in group political activity¹⁶. This approach also enabled us to analyse the dominance of emotional narratives in the political mobilisation of traditionally left-wing electorates by far-right forces. At the same time, the political-anthropological approach was crucial in identifying various motivators, including educational and ethnic differences, which shape the behavioural strategies of voters aligned with both right-wing and left-wing parties¹⁷.

Using case studies from two recent elections – the 2021 Storting election in Norway and the 2022 Riksdag election in Sweden – we analysed the results from multiple perspectives, including ideological divisions, political discourse, ideological and psychological motives, electoral geography, demographics, and economic data.

This systematic analysis allowed us to identify specific voting patterns, including those driven by ideological motivators linked to psychological determinants. It also provided insight into voting behaviours shaped by group identities and political parties' strategies to increase turnout among key voter groups they rely on for support.

2: SWEDEN: PSYCHOPOLITICAL DETERMINANTS OF ELECTORAL ACTIVITY

2-1: STUDY OF POLICY-DRIVEN VOTING PATTERNS

In the 2022 VALU – SVT exit poll survey conducted for the 2022 parliamentary elections¹⁸, the pollsters included questions designed to assess voter perceptions of political parties' positions on various issues. One of the key questions asked was, “Which political party do you believe has the best policies regarding [specific issue]?”

¹⁵ J. Sundberg, “The Enduring Scandinavian Party System”, *Scandinavian Political Studies*, Vol. 22, No. 3 (1999), pp. 221–241. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9477.00014>

¹⁶ V. Melnyk, *In the Captivity of Interpretations: Political Anthropology Between the East and the West*, (Vinnytsya: “New-Book Press”, 2020). <https://books.google.com.ua/books?id=2OafEAAAQBAJ>

¹⁷ D. Sümeghy, “Spatial spillover effects associated with the Sweden Democrats’ growing support”, *Scandinavian Political Studies*, Vol. 47, No. 2 (2024), pp. 172–198. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9477.12268>

¹⁸ Swedish National Data Service, (2022). “<https://snd.se/en/catalogue/dataset/2022-193-1>

These issues, which were highlighted during the campaign, included topics such as the environment, immigration/integration, healthcare, education, tax policy, and others.

The survey covered a broad range of policy areas, including those that directly or indirectly pertain to the economy, such as energy and welfare policies, and broader social and environmental issues impacting Swedish society. The responses reflected participants' views on which party had the most effective approach to addressing each specific issue. To analyse the data, we aggregated the responses based on the political bloc to which each party belongs¹⁹. These blocs are the left-leaning “Red-Green Coalition”, which includes the Social Democrats (S), Left Party (V), and Green Party (MP), and was temporarily allied with the Centre Party (C) during the 2022 Riksdag elections, and the right-leaning coalition, which won the election and now forms the government. The right-wing bloc consists of the Moderate Party (M), Christian Democrats (KD), and Liberals (L), with the support of the Sweden Democrats (SD).

The results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Support for policies on specific issues by electoral bloc and party affiliation

2-2: LEFT-WING MOTIVATORS: THREATS OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND SOCIAL EXCLUSION

Interestingly, according to their coalition name, the parties of the “Red-Green Coalition” (and their policies) have the most substantial support among voters when it

¹⁹ M. Hagevi, “Bloc identification in Multi-Party systems: the case of the Swedish Two-Bloc system”, *West European Politics*, Vol. 38, No. 1 (2014), pp. 73–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2014.911480>

comes to “green issues”, such as environmental protection, climate change mitigation, and matters of social and economic equality.

Two issues where the policies of the left-wing bloc are notably more popular than those of the right by a margin of 20% are the environment (54% support for the policies of left-leaning bloc parties compared to 29% for the right-wing bloc²⁰ and climate change 51% to 28%, respectively²¹.

The political party most associated with the popularity of “green issues” among left-leaning voters is the Green Party of Sweden (MP)²². Although the Greens reject the traditional left-right ideological classification, they have participated in governing coalitions with the centre-left Social Democrats during the first two cabinets of Stefan Löfven (2014–2021), thus aligning with the left-wing parties. In the early 2010s, the Green Party achieved its best electoral result, securing 7.3% of the vote in the 2010 parliamentary elections. At that time, the Greens were particularly popular among younger voters, with 16% of support²³ among those aged 22–30 and 18–21, while gathering only 4% among those over 65. However, by 2022, the Green Party had lost some ground but remained represented in parliament. The significant age gap in support observed in 2010 had diminished mainly, with the party receiving only 5% of support among those aged 18–21, 6% among those aged 22–30, and 4% among those aged 65 and older. These relatively small differences in support reflect a broader shift in Sweden and other European countries, where climate change and environmental issues have become important concerns across all age demographics, no longer primarily the domain of younger voters.

The issue of climate change has consistently ranked among the most important topics during each election cycle since the 2010s. However, it has never emerged as the primary issue in any specific election in Sweden. In the 2010 election, despite the Green Party’s historic result (7.3%), the dominant concerns were economic, stemming from the 2008–2009 financial crisis and subsequent recession. From 2014–2015 onward, immigration became the central issue in political discourse, and during the 2018 election, it emerged as the most polarising and widely discussed issue. This shift in focus toward immigration paved the way for the rise of the Sweden Democrats (SD), who entered the Riksdag for the first time in 2010 with 5.7% of the vote. By 2018, the SD had become the third most popular party, receiving 17.5% of the vote. In contrast, the Green Party did not experience such rapid growth in support during any election cycle, prompting questions about how climate change can serve as a primary driver of electoral behaviour in countries like Sweden and Norway.

²⁰ Swedish National Data Service, (2022).

²¹ SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2022 – Bäst politik, (2022a).
<https://www.svt.se/datajournalistik/valu2022/bast-politik/>

²² N. Aylott and N. Bolin, “The Swedish Greens: a big step forward – and several steps back”, *Environmental Politics*, Vol. 24, No. 2 (2015), pp. 337–341.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2014.1000635>

²³SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Väljargrupper, (2022b).
<https://www.svt.se/datajournalistik/valu2022/valjargrupper/>

Another set of issues where left-wing parties maintain a lead over the right-wing bloc by more than 10% concerns social and economic equality, including gender equality and wealth redistribution through welfare programmes. According to the 2022 VALU report²⁴, despite their loss in the general election, voters preferred the left-wing parties' policies on healthcare and pensions, although by narrower margins of support. This preference is partly due to the pragmatic approach of Swedish political parties, regardless of their ideological stance. Consequently, right-wing parties generally do not oppose most policies associated with the Swedish welfare system, which were primarily implemented by the centre-left Social Democrats, given their broad popularity among the electorate. When comparing the economic policies of Swedish right-wing parties to those of other right-wing parties within Europe and beyond, many of Sweden's policies are characterised as centrist or even centre-left²⁵. Additionally, over the past two decades, the Social Democrats themselves have shifted their economic policies toward the centre, which has contributed to a decline in their support among the working-class electorate – falling from 50% of working-class voters in 2010 to 32% in 2022²⁶.

2-3: RIGHT-WING MOTIVATORS: ISSUES OF IMMIGRATION, INTEGRATION AND SECURITY

The popularity of the left-wing bloc on issues such as climate change can be attributed to the Green Party (MP) being part of the coalition, and a similar dynamic can be observed with the Sweden Democrats (SD), whose de facto inclusion in the right-wing alliance has led to their prominence on the issue of immigration and integration. 29% of respondents²⁷ in a recent survey indicated that they consider the Sweden Democrats' policies to be the most effective on immigration. The rise of the Sweden Democrats to electoral success can largely be attributed to their anti-immigration rhetoric. Prior to 2014, both the left-wing bloc parties (Left Party [V], Social Democrats [S], and Green Party [MP]) and the centre-right Alliance for Sweden (Name of the coalition including M, C, KD, L that existed from 2004 to 2019) parties (Moderates, Liberals, Christian Democrats, and Centre Party) predominantly highlighted the positive contributions of immigration to Swedish society. As such, before 2010, no party in the Riksdag attempted to appeal to the growing anti-immigration sentiment increasingly politicised in Sweden.

The Sweden Democrats (SD) emerged as that party, seeing their support grow from 5.7% in 2010 to 12.9% in 2014 and 17.5% in 2018. During these three election

²⁴ Swedish National Data Service, (2022).

²⁵ O. C. Norocel, "Populist radical right protectors of the folkhem: Welfare chauvinism in Sweden", *Critical Social Policy*, Vol. 36, No. 3 (2016), pp. 371–390. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018315621991>

²⁶ SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Vålgårgrupper, (2022b).

²⁷ SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Vålgårgrupper, (2022b).

cycles, the Sweden Democrats were subject to a “*cordon sanitaire*”²⁸, meaning that all other political parties refused to engage in coalition negotiations with them. This impasse led to a deadlock in coalition talks in 2018, which was eventually resolved in 2019 when the Social Democrats (S) and Greens (MP) remained in government with the passive support of the Left Party and two parties from the centre-right Alliance for Sweden: the Centre Party (C) and the Liberals (L). This development effectively broke the centre-right coalition and initiated a realignment in Swedish electoral politics²⁹.

Since 2018, the other two members of the Alliance for Sweden – Moderates (M) and Christian Democrats (KD) – have openly discussed the possibility of cooperating with the Sweden Democrats while also hardening their own parties’ policies on immigration in an attempt to appeal to some of the Sweden Democrats’ voter base. As immigration continued to be a dominant issue in the election cycle, the newly formed coalition of Moderates, Liberals, and Christian Democrats, with the support of the Sweden Democrats, won the 2022 election and assumed power. It is also noteworthy that voter turnout in Sweden decreased by 3% from 87% in 2018 to 84% in 2022, which may have benefited the Sweden Democrats³⁰.

In Sweden’s political discourse, the issue of immigration is associated with the issue of integration, and the problem of integration is frequently associated with law and order. Many areas designated as “vulnerable” by the Swedish Police Authority are districts with a high concentration of immigrants and refugees. These two issues – immigration and integration – are those on which the policies of the right-wing bloc are more popular than those of the left-wing bloc. This is, in part, because Social Democrat-led governments were responsible for handling, accommodating, and integrating migrants during the refugee crisis that affected Europe in the mid-2010s. They were perceived to have failed in doing so.

3: NORWAY: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC ASPECTS OF ELECTORAL IDENTITIES

²⁸ J. E. Axelsen, “The cordon sanitaire: a social norm-based model”, *Journal of Elections Public Opinion and Parties*, Vol. 34, No. 2 (2023), pp. 277–297.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17457289.2023.2168272>

²⁹ L. Olander, “Sweden gets new government after four months of negotiations”, *Current Affairs*, (2019). <https://www.thenewfederalist.eu/sweden-gets-new-government-after-four-months-of-negotiations?lang=fr>

³⁰ Y. Choe and E. B. Tambe, “Turnout Drop in Times of Crisis? An enigma of the electoral turnout change in the 2022 parliamentary election in Sweden”, *Korean Scandinavian Society*, Vol. 1, No. 30 (2022), pp. 75–103.

3-1: ECONOMIC IDENTITIES: WORKING-CLASS MOBILISATION VS. ECONOMIC VOTING-DRIVEN HIGH TURNOUT

Economic identity, traditionally associated with the left, specifically the “working class”, plays a significant role in shaping electoral behaviour. A prominent example of how collective identity influences voting patterns can be found in the success of social-democratic parties in both Sweden and Norway. For instance, the Social-Democratic Workers’ Party of Sweden (S) maintained continuous political dominance from 1936 to 1976, winning elections for 40 years without interruption. Similarly, the Labour Party of Norway (Ap), also known as the Workers’ Party, held power uninterrupted from 1935 to 1963, securing nearly three decades of governance.

A significant challenge and disruption to the electoral activity of the Labour Party occurred during the Nazi occupation, from April 8, 1940, to May 9, 1945. During this period, the Nazi administration declared the ultranationalist *Nasjonal Samling* the sole legal political party³¹ within the occupied *Reichskommissariat Norwegen*. Vidkun Quisling led the party³², a staunch opponent of the Labour Party and a proponent of political integration with Nazi Germany.

During World War II, the Labour Party assumed a leadership role in the resistance movement, which gained significant traction across various regions of Norway. The active institutional collaboration further strengthened the political ties between Norwegian social democracy, the monarchy, and the leader of the national movement, King Haakon VII (1905–1957)³³. Notably, Johan Nygaardsvold served as the formal Prime Minister of the Kingdom (1935–1945) during the Nazi occupation, leading his cabinet from London.

However, the Labour Party’s primary successes in mobilising the electorate were more clearly demonstrated after the war, when Einar Gerhardsen held the office of Prime Minister across multiple terms, from 1945 to 1951, 1955 to 1963, and 1963 to 1965. Under his leadership, the Kingdom of Norway transitioned into a state with a planned economy³⁴.

³¹ M. K. Hamre, “‘Organic unity through a new order’: Ideas of corporatism and the Norwegian *Nasjonal Samling*”, *Laboratoire italien*, Vol. 32: Le corporatisme fasciste à l’étranger, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.4000/1221f>

³² K. B. Simonsen, “Vidkun Quisling, antisemittismen og den paranoide stil”, *Historisk tidsskrift*, Vol. 96 No. 4 (2017), pp. 446-467.

³³ K. Krake, “From revolutionary paroles to democratic rhetoric: replacement of the political vocabulary within the Norwegian Labour Party in the interwar period”, *Scandinavian Journal of History*, Vol. 48, No. 3 (2022), pp. 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03468755.2022.2125435>

³⁴ E. Lange, H. Pharo, “Planning and economic Policy in Norway, 1945-1960”, *Scandinavian Journal of History*, Vol. 16, No. 3 (2008), pp. 215–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03468759108579219>

From 1948 onward, Norway introduced administrative and economic *four-year plans*³⁵. In this context, the Labour Party not only drew upon the experiences of contemporary European communist parties but also integrated specific economic models from the Nazi occupation period. Einar Gerhardsen gained widespread recognition as the “Father of the Nation” (*Landsfaderen*), and the Labour Party’s parliamentary result in the 1957 elections reached 48.3%. These successes were primarily driven by strong support from the working class³⁶.

How did the Social Democrats consistently mobilise high voter turnout among working-class citizens? A key factor lies in the role of labour unions and their strategic alliances with the Social Democrats in Sweden and the Labour Party in Norway. Throughout the 20th century, labour unions were central in mobilising voters, predominantly benefiting left-leaning political parties^{37, 38}.

Labour unions that consistently endorsed and coordinated with specific political parties established a clear link between an individual’s occupation and economic stability and the political party aligned with the union. However, by the late 20th century, labour unions began to lose influence over the electorate, contributing to a decline in electoral success for social democratic parties. For example, the Labour Party of Norway consistently secured at least 34.3% of the vote in every election held during the latter half of the 20th century. In contrast, in the 21st century, the party exceeded its worst 20th-century result only once – during the 2009 Storting election, when it received 35.4%. In the 2021 election, however, the Labour Party secured only 26.3%.

The weakening of labour unions as practical mobilisation tools is a primary factor in the decline of social democratic influence. Another significant factor contributing to this decline is the shift of working-class voters from centre-left parties to anti-immigration, right-wing populist movements. Data from demographic groups in the Swedish elections demonstrates this trend: In 2022, the Social-Democratic Party (S) received 32% of the working-class vote, with the Sweden Democrats (SD) trailing closely at 29%³⁹. In contrast, in 2002, the Social Democrats captured 50% of the working-class vote, with the Left Party (V) coming in second at 14%. This shift highlights that the electorate gained by the Sweden Democrats (SD), the most right-

³⁵ E. Erichsen, “Economic Planning and Policies in Norway”, *Challenge*, Vol. 20, No. 6 (1978), pp. 5–13. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40719596>

³⁶ F. Sejersted, “Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy. In M. B. Adams (Ed.). *The Age of Social Democracy: Norway and Sweden in the Twentieth Century*, (Princeton: Princeton University Press (Chapter 10, p. 289–330), 2011). <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400839124-013>

³⁷ H. Finseraas and K. Vernby, “A mixed blessing for the left? Early voting, turnout and election outcomes in Norway”, *Electoral Studies*, Vol. 33 (2013), pp. 278–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electstud.2013.07.003>

³⁸ K. Sass, “How to sit on Two Sides of the Table? Swedish and Norwegian Unions’ Approaches to Representative Worker Participation during the 20th Century”, *Nordic journal of working life studies*, Vol. 4, No. 3 (2014). <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/4f92/88e11c9f1acd03783157bec1a183d64a8fb7.pdf>

³⁹ SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Vålgargrupper, (2022b).

wing political force, was not traditionally aligned with the right. The electorate of centre-right parties may differ significantly from that of voters supporting the Progress Party (FrP) in Norway or the Sweden Democrats (SD) in Sweden.

Individualist economic voting patterns, which tend to provide consistent support for political parties, are most commonly associated with the political right. Using Norway as an example, the voter turnout in the 2021 Storting elections was 77.2% nationwide⁴⁰. Notably, a clear correlation exists between higher income levels and increased voter turnout. For instance, in the region with the highest median household income, Akershus⁴¹, the turnout was 79.1%. Akershus, which includes the suburbs of Oslo, exhibits higher support for centre-right economically liberal-conservative parties, such as Høyre (literally “The Right” or “Conservative Party”). In the 2021 Storting election, Høyre received 20.4% of the national vote, but in Akershus, they garnered 27.4% – a 7% increase over their national result.

A closer examination of municipal-level results in Akershus, particularly in Bærum municipality, further illustrates the influence of economic factors on voter turnout. Bærum is consistently ranked among the wealthiest municipalities in Norway, with a mean household income of 974,000 NOK in 2022, according to Statistics Norway⁴². As the second wealthiest municipality in the country, Bærum recorded a turnout of 83.9% in the 2021 Storting elections – 6.7% higher than the national average. In this constituency, Høyre won with 40.3% of the vote.

In 2022, the wealthiest municipality in Norway was Sola, located in Rogaland County, with a mean household income of 959,000 NOK, according to SSB⁴³. Sola’s voter turnout was 79.7%, higher than the regional and national averages. In this municipality, Høyre secured 30.5% of the vote, while the more right-wing⁴⁴ Progress Party (FrP) came in second with 20.3%.

Despite its relative stability in both Sweden and Norway, economic voting is also influenced by political crises in these countries⁴⁵, often driven by the politicisation of more emotionally charged issues. However, the economic voting patterns of upper-

⁴⁰ Valgresultat, (2021).

⁴¹ Statistics Norway. *Median inntekt etter skatt, etter fylke og husholdningstype. Kroner*, (n.d.). <https://www.ssb.no/97014/median-inntekt-etter-skatt-etter-fylke-og-husholdningstype.kroner>

⁴² Statistics Norway. *Income and wealth statistics for households. Bærum municipality*, (2022a). <https://www.ssb.no/en/statbank/table/06944/tableViewLayout1/>

⁴³ Statistics Norway. *Innvandrere og stortingsvalget 2021. Stemmeberettigede, valgdeltakelse, partivalg og representanter*, (2022b). <https://www.ssb.no/valg/stortingsvalg/artikler/innvandrere-og-stortingsvalget-2021>

⁴⁴ J. Bjerkem, “The Norwegian Progress Party: An Established Populist Party”, *European View*, Vol. 15, No. 2 (2016), pp. 233–243. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12290-016-0404-8>

⁴⁵ C. J. Anderson, “The End of Economic Voting? Contingency Dilemmas and the Limits of Democratic Accountability”, *Annual Review of Political Science*, Vol. 10, No. 1 (2007), pp. 271–296. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.10.050806.155344>

middle-class and middle-class voters remain a significant mobilising factor for the electoral bases of certain political parties.

It is interesting to trace, in particular, support for political parties at the parliamentary election in Norway in 2021, by income level (see Figure 2).

The Conservative Party was by far the most popular among people who earned at least 900,000 Norwegian kroner yearly in the country’s 2021 parliamentary election. In this income bracket, 38% of voters supported the Conservative Party. Both the Red Party and the Socialist Left Party did better here than among the groups with higher incomes, while the situation was more mixed among those with yearly incomes under 300,000 kroner. One can suggest that this ‘picture’ reflects the phenomenon described by Torben Worre in 1980 – “class parties and class voting in the Scandinavian countries”⁴⁶.

Figure 2. Support for political parties at the parliamentary election in Norway in 2021, by income level

Source:⁴⁷

3-2: SOCIAL AND CULTURAL IDENTITIES: EDUCATIONAL AND ETHNIC DIFFERENTIATORS

⁴⁶ T. Worre, “Class Parties and Class Voting in the Scandinavian Countries”, *Scandinavian Political Studies*, Bind 3 (1980).

https://tidsskrift.dk/scandinavian_political_studies/article/download/32365/30179?inline=1

⁴⁷ E. Dyvik, “Support for parties in the parliamentary election in Norway 2021, by income”, *Statista*, (2024). <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1326532/support-for-parties-in-norway-income-level/>

One social identity that is not frequently discussed but undeniably exists is educational identity, which is based on the level of education of the electorate. In the 2021 exit poll conducted during the Storting election, results were divided into three groups based on education levels: voters with incomplete secondary education (“Grunnskole”), voters with complete secondary education (“Videregående”), and voters with a university degree⁴⁸. While party support among different education groups varies, the most significant difference is observed in the results for the Progress Party (FrP).

Despite its name, the Progress Party (FrP) is the most conservative in the Storting and experiences the most significant decline in support among university graduates. The Progress Party (FrP) received only 4.4% support from this group, compared to 15.9% among those with complete secondary education and 18.6% among those with incomplete secondary education.

One possible explanation for this disparity is that, while anti-immigration parties often employ the “*us vs. them*” rhetoric to create a divide between the “native” working class and the immigrant working class in order to gain support from the former, highly educated voters tend to reject these narratives. *This is likely because higher-educated individuals are more likely to be employed in specialised fields, which “are not seen as being at risk of being overtaken by immigrants”*.

Thus, it can be argued that opposition to far-right parties among the highly educated electorate also constitutes a form of group-identity voting despite this group’s broad nature.

Another form of *group-identity voting* may be based on cultural or ethnic factors. For instance, in the 2021 exit poll, the Labour Party of Norway (Ap) received 25.7% support overall, while it garnered 39.2% support⁴⁹. From voters with an immigration background. The highest levels of support for the Labour Party (AP) and left-wing parties, in general, came from voters of African and Asian backgrounds. Among voters with an African migration background, the Labour Party received 51.7%, followed by the Socialist Left Party with 21.0%, the Conservatives with 9.2%, and the Red Party (Rødt) with 5.2%⁵⁰. Among voters with Asian and Turkish backgrounds, the Labour Party received 45.7%, the Conservatives in second place at 13.9%, and the Socialist Left Party in third with 11.7%.

This disproportionate support for particular parties from different immigrant background groups reflects another case of group-identity voting based on shared cultural or ethnic backgrounds. Issues of race and ethnicity are particularly salient in these cases, as pro-multicultural, left-wing parties dominate among non-European

⁴⁸ Statistics Norway, (2022a).

⁴⁹ Statistics Norway, (2022b).

⁵⁰ E. H. Allern, “The Contemporary Relationship of ‘New Left’ and ‘New Right’ Parties with Interest Groups: Exceptional or Mainstream? The Case of Norway’s Socialist Left and Progress Party”, *Scandinavian Political Studies*, Vol. 36, No. 1 (2012), pp. 67–90.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9477.2012.00297.x>

electorates. At the same time, immigrants from other Nordic or European countries tend to support the most anti-immigration party, the Progress Party (FrP), at a higher rate than voters without an immigration background. The Progress Party received 11.6% in the 2021 election and 11.9% in the exit poll conducted during the election. However, it garnered 17.7% support from voters with a Nordic migration background and 19.4% from those who had migrated from other Western European countries⁵¹.

This phenomenon is not exclusive to Norway or Sweden; it is also observed in other countries, where immigrants from wealthier nations tend to vote for nominally anti-immigration parties in their new countries of residence. In addition to group-identity voting, the processes of agitation and voter mobilisation further contribute to different voting patterns among various immigrant-background groups⁵².

4-DISCUSSION

4-1: IMPLICATIONS OF ELECTORAL CONTEXT

For instance, the Swedish and Norwegian electoral contexts allow for identifying phenomena such as *group-based (emotional)*, *economic (individualistic)*, and *institutionally-oriented* voting.

Group-based voting is characterised by the social attitude of “*us vs. them*” and is emotional in its socio-psychological essence. The politicisation of immigration issues between 2014 and 2024 became a key factor in the mobilisation of a segment of the “working class” by right-wing political parties. Consequently, a significant portion of the potentially left-leaning electorate dramatically shifted their preferences, perceiving the roots of real or imagined economic problems in a labour market open to immigration. For such voters from the working-class milieu, an entirely emotional socio-cultural opposition of “*native vs. foreign*” took precedence⁵³.

This anthropological identity scale conceptually contradicts the ideological doctrines of the left spectrum and decisively rejects the socialist slogan of uniting all members of the “working class”⁵⁴. As is well known, the programmes of left-wing

⁵¹ Statistics Norway, (2022).

⁵² J. Ferwerda, H. Finseraas and J. Bergh, “Voting Rights and Immigrant Incorporation: Evidence from Norway”, *British Journal of Political Science*, Vol. 50, No. 2 (2018), pp. 713–730. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007123417000643>

⁵³ K. Loxbo, “How the radical right reshapes public opinion: the Sweden Democrats’ local mobilisation, 2002–2020”, *West European Politics* (2024), pp. 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2024.2396775>

⁵⁴ M. Maayan and C. Boix, “Social Democracy and the Birth of Working-Class Representation in Europe”, *World Politics*, Vol. 76, No. 3 (2024), pp. 499–542. <https://doi.org/10.1353/wp.2024.a933070>

political parties appeal to the ideal of uniting workers regardless of their ethnic background, country of origin, or citizenship. In theory, ideological supporters of left-wing political parties should welcome immigration, particularly if it contributes to improving the material and spiritual well-being of migrants (especially those employed).

In contrast, *economic voting* tends to align with individualistic attitudes and accompanies the process of identity preservation among private owners with relatively high and stable incomes. This type of voting makes voter turnout directly dependent on high-income levels. It seeks to maintain ideological balance by preserving an equidistant neutrality between the visibly growing far-right tendencies and the consistently widespread ideas of social progressivism. However, within the broader landscape of political ideologies, economic voting ultimately lags behind *group-based (emotional) voting* in influencing political outcomes.

4-2: THE ROLE OF INSTITUTIONS

The principles governing political systems and the specific features of some aspects of constitutional law in Sweden and Norway allow particular attention to be paid to *institutionally oriented voting*⁵⁵. Throughout the 20th century, *labour unions* emerged as a dominant social force tasked with shaping the economic attitudes of voters by advocating for the protection of rights and social security entitlements for their members. In the latter half of the 20th century, their activities became an integral component of the political culture in Sweden and Norway⁵⁶.

The combination of moderation and efficiency in the organisational activities of labour unions served as a cornerstone of Swedish and Norwegian social-democratic mythmaking. When external observers and political scientists frequently refer to the “social democracy” of the Norwegian or Swedish model, they essentially reference the image of labour unions that excelled in labour socialisation and facilitating interactions between individual citizens and bureaucratic institutions. Despite a noticeable decline in the popularity of social-democratic political forces compared to their achievements in the 1930s–1970s, it would be a mistake to regard labour unions as merely a historical phenomenon.

Today, labour unions remain significant both as a symbol and as an institution that upholds the socio-psychological identification of the working class with social-democratic parties. That said, labour unions have undergone several qualitative transformations over the decades, notably during the 1980s, the 2008–2009 financial crisis, and their favourable stance on immigrant integration after 2014–2015. These

⁵⁵ N. Bolin, M. Grusell and L. Nord, “Second thoughts on digital first: Exploring the development of election campaigning among Swedish political parties, 2010-2022”, *Nordicom Review*, Vol. 45, No. S1 (2024), 15–35. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2024-0006>

⁵⁶ A. A. Ray and J. G. Pontusson, “Trade unions and the partisan preferences of their members: Sweden 1976–2021”, *Socio-Economic Review*, Vol. 23, No. 1 (2025), pp. 51–73. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwae027>

developments significantly weaken the future mobilisation potential of institutional voting and signal a profound transformation in the identity and self-perception of the working class in both nations⁵⁷.

CONCLUSION

5:

Policy-related polling analysis reveals that major electoral issues driving voter participation correspond closely with the ideological orientations of left-wing and right-wing electoral blocs.

Left-wing parties' policies enjoy the greatest support for environmental concerns and social and economic equality issues. Over the past 15 years, demographic support for these policies has shifted, with the electorate of the Green Party (MP) ageing and younger generations increasingly gravitating toward new political parties^{58, 59}. Despite this generational shift, the historical achievements of the largest party in the left-wing coalition, the Social Democrats (S), continue to be leveraged as a tool to secure support from older voters. The Social Democrats remain by far the most popular party among those aged 65 and older, receiving 38% of their support, while the Sweden Democrats (SD) hold second place with only 20%⁶⁰.

Conversely, right-wing parties' policies are most popular on issues of immigration and law and order. This shift resulted from the de facto inclusion of the Sweden Democrats (SD) into the right-wing coalition after 12 years of the party being under a "cordon sanitaire"⁶¹. The Sweden Democrats have developed a distinct electorate that is no longer entirely aligned with other right-wing parties, particularly given their growing popularity and strong second-place position among the working-class electorate, trailing only the Social Democrats (S)⁶².

The study of the correlation between the transformation of electoral outcomes for different political parties in parliamentary elections facilitates the differentiation of three distinct models of electoral behaviour:

- a model driven by emotional factors (group-based voting);
- a model driven by individualistic factors (economic voting);

⁵⁷ P. Rathgeb and M. B. Klitgaard, "Protagonists or consenters: radical right parties and attacks on trade unions", *Journal of European Public Policy*, Vol. 29, No. 7 (2022), pp. 1049–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2021.1916060>

⁵⁸ N. Aylott and N. Bolin, (2015).

⁵⁹ H. Rattinger and M. Steinbrecher, "Economic voting in times of economic crisis", *German Politics*, Vol. 20, No. 1 (2011), pp. 128–145. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644008.2011.554111>

⁶⁰ SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Vålgargrupper, (2022b).

⁶¹ J. E. Axelsen, (2023).

⁶² SVT-NYHETER. VALU 2010 – Vålgargrupper, (2022b).

- a model driven by trade unions or organisational orientation (institutionally oriented voting).

The methodological significance of all three models lies in applying the social-psychological *Law of Effect*. Empirical evidence further supports the correlation between ideological slogans and electoral behavioural responses. For example, *group-based voting* can be attributed to the far-right's strategic appeal to emotions associated with *national identity* and concerns over *job questions*, particularly regarding competition with foreign workers. The emotional resonance of their messaging and clear explanations have prompted a shift among former moderate voters of Swedish and Norwegian social democrats toward supporting right-wing parties. The social value of ultra-right political parties, therefore, lies in their ability to foster and contrast a collective identity with other cultures.

The *economic, behavioural model*, in contrast, is grounded in the principles of individualism and aligns with the *left-Hegelian ideas* of Max Stirner. Unlike group-based voting, individualistic voting typically disregards collective identity and class struggle, focusing instead on pursuing an *egoistic balance* between conflicting political discourses. Its primary objective is to secure an individual's position within the economic system. This model gained prominence during transitional periods in Scandinavian social democracy in the 1990s and 2000s. However, as immigration issues increasingly dominated political discourse in Sweden and Norway, attention shifted from economic concerns to socio-cultural dynamics. This shift diminished the influence of economic voting models, while group-based emotional dynamics – such as the “*us vs. them*” mentality – gained traction.

The *institutionally-oriented model* has historically been closely tied to the economic behavioural model, as both are rooted in material interests. However, the institutionally-oriented model emphasises the value-driven foundation of socio-economic orientation. It is based on a sense of collective identity but avoids emotional opposition to other socio-cultural groups. Instead, this model centres on fostering a sense of security and social protection. This sense of solidarity is achieved through unity with other members of the labour sector. Within the Scandinavian *welfare state*, labour unions have historically played a central role in organising this model of electoral behaviour. Labour unions provided a psychological bastion of security and social stability. However, the socio-cultural challenges posed by immigration have weakened this role, prompting a shift in the working class's political alignment from centre-left to far-right policies. Consequently, the capacity of labour unions to mobilise the working class has diminished, and determined by cultural traditions ideological slogans have become more effective in rallying voters than stable social organisms.

Finally, voter turnout driven by economic voting remains relatively stable among the centrist-right electorate. High-income regions continue to support centrist-right liberal-conservative parties. In contrast, changes in voter mobilisation strategies and the growing politicisation of immigration issues have contributed to a *distinct submodel of group voting*. This submodel is particularly evident among ethnic and national

minorities (e.g., individuals of migrant origin) and groups with varying levels of education.

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